

DEVELOPMENT OF SELF HEALING COMPOSITE MATERIALS: FABRICATION AND MICRO-STRUCTURAL ANALYSES

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SUMMARY

A custom resin transfer molding (RTM) method for the fabrication of carbon fiber composites using thermally reversible highly cross linked polymeric matrices was developed. The resulting material quality and healing efficiency was assessed using X-ray phase contrast micro-tomography. The X-ray investigations revealed that partial healing of extended cracks occurred in samples that were kept at 90°C for 2 hours.

Keywords: self healing, carbon fiber composites, RTM, micro-tomography, thermo-mechanical characterization

OVERVIEW

Artificially engineered materials made of multiple components are specifically designed to attain properties that exceed those of the individual constituents. Among the advantages of composites prevalent in the aerospace and biomedical engineering fields are larger strength-to-weight ratios, design flexibility, cost, resistance to fatigue damage, favorable damping characteristics, corrosion resistance and low thermal expansion. As a result of these properties, a wide range of commercial applications are seen today. These materials have unique advantages over their monolithic constituent materials and remarkable adaptability to their intended function, but just as in nature, these materials do fail. Often the growth of micro-failures can become critical. Once incipient cracks have formed, the structural integrity can become significantly compromised. If micro-crack development is identified at an early stage different techniques can be considered to prevent or arrest the growth of failure mechanisms within the resin. Inspired by the optimized mechanisms of self repair that nature has provided to living organisms, the concept of an autonomous self-healing material, where the initiation of repair is an intrinsic characteristic of the material itself, has become of interest in recent years for its application in composite materials.

The state of the art of the various self-healing technologies currently developed for fiber reinforced polymeric (FRP) composites are primarily attempts to mimic natural healing through detailed studies of natural processes. Two primary approaches have been recently developed to effect self healing in FRP systems.

First, self-healing can be realized by forming new chemical bonds within the material by inducing *in situ* polymerization of monomers that are released locally to polymerize

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and form a new material. In this method, hollow microspheres are integrated into the matrix. The spheres contain a monomer that cures when in contact with another monomer (catalyst) dispersed into the composite matrix. A propagating crack encounters a microcapsule shell, breaking the shell and releasing the monomer to flow along the crack surfaces. Upon contacting the catalyst, the monomer polymerizes to heal the microcrack as demonstrated by White et al. (2001) [2-5].

An alternative approach to this self-repair mechanism is based on the recent demonstration of Chen et al.'s (2002) [6-7] that certain new classes of polymers can be thermally re-mended at temperatures below their softening points. These polymeric matrices can be repaired multiple times by restoring the same chemical bonds that are broken during damage events. Such a composite matrix is a reversible Diels–Alder (DA) cross linking polymer. Wudl and co-workers prepared a highly cross linked, thermally-remendable polymer in which all of the intermolecular links and cross links are formed using Diels-Alder chemistry [1]. The first system they developed used tris-maleimide (3M) and a tetra-furan (4F) and subsequently they employed tetra-furan (4F) together with bis-maleimide (2MEP) to form a healable polymer. This approach afforded a simple way to prepare remendable polymers which can go through repeated cycles of cracking and healing. Moreover, the mechanical properties of these polymers are very close to those of some thermosetting matrices common in the aerospace industry. Thus these materials are attractive candidates as stiff, tough and self repairable composite matrices. Although the pure polymer properties have been characterized, little work is present in the literature that provides insight into appropriate fabrication techniques, properties and microstructure of fiber reinforced composites using this class of healable matrices [8].

A custom resin transfer method for the fabrication of fiber reinforced composites with healable polymers based on reversible DA and retro-DA cycloaddition mechanisms, was developed and is briefly described in this work.

Since it is known that the properties of the composite materials strongly depend on the quality of the fabrication method, we have assessed the microstructure of the material, characterized defects and monitored healing efficiency through X-ray phase contrast micro-tomography. Some results on the thermo-mechanical characterization of the composite material are also presented to guide the selection of the temperature used in the healing thermo-cycle.

FABRICATION OF SELF HEALING COMPOSITES

In this work the polymer 2MEP4F was used as the matrix for the fabrication of carbon fiber reinforced polymeric (CFRP) composites. The final properties and performance of the composite strongly depend on the fabrication process which, in this work, is a modified resin transfer molding (RTM) technique. The apparatus developed for the fabrication of carbon fiber composite, is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Left aluminum mold and resulting composite panel; right: custom injection system for high temperature RTM fabrication of self-healing carbon fiber composites.

Two characteristics of the 2MEP4F polymer present fabrication challenges. The first is that one component (2MEP) is a solid at room temperature and must be heated to become liquid. The second characteristic is the relatively rapid polymerization rate of the two liquid phase monomers upon mixing. Therefore the injection of the resin into the dry carbon fiber layers must be done in a short time frame and at an elevated temperature. The injection system indicated in Figure 1 is composed of two separate chambers in which the two polymer constituents are placed. Stepper motors independently drive the pistons in each chamber under displacement control so that each monomer is pushed into the aluminum mixing tube in the correct stoichiometric ratio. The two monomers are combined and mixed immediately prior to injection into the mold where fabric layers of carbon fibers are placed. T300 unidirectional carbon fiber fabric (PAN precursor) supplied by Fiberglass Supply (California, USA) was used for the fabrication of the material. The application of vacuum during the fabrication process prevents the formation of air voids inside the material. The entire system, including the monomer chambers, the mixing tube, and the mold are heated and thermally regulated within 1° C.

This apparatus affords us the opportunity to fabricate the different types of samples that are needed in order to characterize and quantify both the material quality and its healing efficiency defined as the capability to mend internal micro-failures upon application of heat. 10x10 cm panels with different lay-ups were fabricated and samples were cut for tensile testing and dynamic mechanical analyses in double or single cantilever beam. In this paper the results obtained from the micro-structural investigations of carbon fiber samples with 2MEP4F healable matrix are presented.

MATERIALS PROPERTIES AND MICROSTRUCTURE

The mechanical material response as a function of temperature needs to be considered when selecting the temperature at which the internal micro-failures in the material are to be repaired. To provide this information, dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) experiments were conducted with a DMS Seiko 6100 using the double cantilever beam method at a temperature rate of 3°C per minute and imposed strain amplitude with frequency of 1Hz.

In Figure 2 the thermo-mechanical response at a frequency of 1Hz of a [0/90/0] sample fabricated using the previously described method and subjected to a temperature ramp from room temperature up to 90°C is presented. The figure shows the behavior of the storage modulus normalized to its room temperature value, and Tan Delta (ratio between the material loss modulus E'' and the material storage modulus E') versus

temperature. It is observed that the modulus progressively decreases with increasing temperature, and has a 10% overall reduction at 75°C. The storage modulus becomes significantly lower than its value at room temperature as the glass transition region is approached, i.e. above 105°C. Above this temperature the dissipation properties of the material become dominant. For this reason the samples described below (e.g., Figure 3) along with all of the samples cryo-shocked for the X-ray tomography investigations, were healed at a temperature lower than the characteristic glass transition temperature of the 2MEP4F polymer, 105°C.

Figure 2 Dynamic mechanical analysis of [0/90/0] 2MEP4F laminated composite at 1Hz and temperature rate of 3C/minute. The material storage modulus, E' , normalized with its value at room temperature, $E'(RT)$, and Tan Delta (loss modulus/storage modulus) are plotted as functions of temperature

The samples fabricated with the method described above were analyzed by X-ray phase contrast micro-tomography. The application of X-ray tomography has been used for the 3D reconstruction of 2x2mm samples, including pure polymeric samples and composites coupons using the 2MEP4F polymer, and for analyzing the volumetric distribution of fibers, flaws, defects and the eventual presence of micro-cracks. The capability of accurately mapping, in three dimensions, the presence of volumetric defects such as cracks induced by external loads is of help in determining the healing efficiency of the composite material following the application of the healing thermocycles. Comparisons of samples pre- and post-healing can provide understanding of the characteristic crack density, propagation and related phenomena.

These studies were performed using low energy synchrotron radiation (15keV). Beam exposure time and detector distance were optimized to achieve maximum contrast among the different material constituents (carbon fibers, resin and voids). The technique has been successfully used in past studies [9-11] to overcome the difficulties in conducting high spatial resolution X-ray investigations on materials with relatively low X-ray absorption such as the polymer under investigation here. The analyses on the CFRP 2MEP4F material were performed at the Advanced Photon Source (APS) at Argonne National Laboratories (Illinois, USA).

The micro-structural investigations were conducted on samples of carbon fiber laminated [0/90/0] composites. A good distribution of the fibers into the resin and a limited number of voids were observed (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 X-ray micro-tomography of [0/90/0] 2MEP4F S3_2 sample; projection of the sample facing the beam radiation (left) and one reconstructed slice (right).

In Figure 3, the projection of a [0/90/0] healable sample (designated S3_2) fabricated using the method described in the previous section is presented. In this projection one reconstructed orthogonal slice, with a resolution of 1 μm, was selected and is presented on the right. A very limited number of small voids are visible in this reconstructed section. Some of them have been marked with red circles. It is important to note that different gray scale colors resulting from the phase contrast technique applied to the sample are given by the different atomic mass of the constituents in such a way that heavier materials are brighter while the black regions correspond to the absence of material. The grey area around the coupon is due to the absorption of the material of the rotary stage on top of which the sample is placed. It is of interest that the edges of the coupon appear clearly damaged. Visible delamination of fibers at the edges has been found in all scanned samples and can be attributed to the cutting method.

Through the analysis of the images conducted on different slices belonging to the same sample, the average void fraction was estimated to be no greater than 1.2%.

Using the same technique, we were able to identify cracks within the samples and qualitatively evaluate the healing efficiency of the composite material after the application of different healing thermo-cycles. Samples that were quenched in liquid nitrogen to induce distributed micro-cracks were scanned and then healed at the constant temperature of about 90°C for varying intervals of time. Following each healing cycle, the samples were again imaged.

A sample that was cracked before the X-ray inspection is shown in Figure 4 on the left hand side. The crack in the center is clearly visible in the orthogonal view shown below the vertical projection of the sample. The extension of the crack through the thickness is visible from the projection view. The images on the right hand side of Figure 4 show images following a healing cycle. It is qualitatively observed that partial healing has taken place.

Figure 4 $[0]_3$ 2MEP4F sample with central crack: vertical projection and orthogonal view. The sample was kept in an oven at 86°C for two hours.

CONCLUSIONS

The healing properties and efficiency of polymeric materials based on thermally reversible Diels-Alder crosslinking have been previously discussed and demonstrated in the literature. In this work a modified RTM method for the fabrication of a self-healing composite material using this healable polymer matrix is described. The thermo-mechanical properties of the healable composite were investigated in order to select the temperature for the application of a suitable healing thermo-cycle. Also, the material microstructure was assessed through X-ray tomography investigations of 2MEP4F CFRP samples.

From these experiments two major conclusions can be drawn. First, the material clearly displays a drop of stiffness when the temperature approaches the glass transition temperature of the matrix polymer. This suggests that an ideal healing cycle should be conducted at temperatures which do not affect the structural performance of the material, particularly in cases where the healing is carried out while the component is subjected to external loads. Second, we were able to evaluate the material quality through the analysis of the X-ray reconstructed images and presence of distributed voids was observed to be less than 1.2%. Reconstructed three dimensional images also demonstrated healing of microcracks within CFRP samples. Continuing studies to quantify the volumetric presence of cracks and the healing efficiency of carbon fiber composites samples using X-ray tomography are currently being carried out at APS, Argonne National Laboratories.

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